

Satisfaction on English Language Learning with Online System

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Abstract—The objective is to study the satisfaction on English with an online learning. Online learning system mainly consists of English lessons, exercises, tests, web boards, and supplementary lessons for language practice. The sample groups are 80 Thai students studying English for Business Communication, majoring in Hotel and Lodging Management. The data are analyzed by mean, standard deviation (S.D.) value from the questionnaires. The results were found that the most average of satisfaction on academic aspects are technological searching tool through E-learning system that support the students' learning (4.51), knowledge evaluation on pre-post learning and teaching (4.45), and change for project selections according to their interest, subject contents including practice in the real situations (4.45), respectively.

Keywords— English Learning, Online System, Satisfaction.

I. INTRODUCTION

ENGLISH is important as a world language. It increasingly plays role in all countries around the world that caused by the world changes especially the economy and society. The economic competition and expansion in the new effective markets has continually occurred. However, there is a serious problem of Thai people that is the obstacle on English communication. Further than this, learning is not limited in only the classroom, using internet is worldwide in terms of convenience, rapidness, and virtually system.

Nowadays, teaching English focuses on communication approach or communicate capability. It bases on teaching procedures and communicational evaluation and learning objective of today teaching is focusing on communication development including suitable and acceptable language for those societies. The communication approach contains communication theories, grammars, situations and human psychology [1].

Many teaching methods are used to develop language learning. Learners' needs in each area of development are cognitive, linguistic, social, emotional, and physical. It leads to learner or student-centered learning that is a wide variety of educational programs, learning experiences, instructional approaches, and academic-support strategies that are intended to address the distinct learning needs, interests, aspirations, or cultural background of individual students and groups of students. E-learning is widely used to develop language ability. It can be defined as learning facilitated and supported through the use of information and communications technology.

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It covers the use of computers and technology as a vehicle for knowledge exchange within teaching and learning. It broadly benefits for an additional avenue with which to support teaching and learning practice in terms of: 1) the ability to provide distance learning (learning not on campus), 2) a blended learning/teaching approach (using face-to-face and technology), and 3) the use of technology to support a wide range of educational activity. It provides many opportunities including large scale online delivery of module and courses. The development growth of technology-mediated learning systems has created a whole new learning environment that enables students to increase their achievement and academic encouragement. E-learning instruction is the integration between present technology and teaching design to increasing learning effectiveness and to solve the limitation on time and places. It attributes to manage the environment for learning and teaching encouragement and giving support. It can be involved in some parts or whole parts of teaching process [2]-[4].

II. OBJECTIVES

This study aims to create an online learning system for business communication using English and to survey the students' satisfaction on using applied English for Business Communication with an Online Learning System on following aspects: convenience, academy, teaching strategy, facilitator, and student -centered learning.

III. METHOD

The sampling groups are 80 junior students majoring in Hotel and Lodging Management, Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University, and registering in for English for Business Communication.

Data are collected by an online questionnaire for learners satisfactory on English language learning with online system. Collecting data process is (1) analyze the course content, design the exercises, tests, and questionnaires (2) construct the exercises, tests, questionnaires and a lesson manual (3) try out the lessons that the researcher constructed (4) evaluate the students' satisfaction on online lessons (5) report the results.

The research instrument is the questionnaire on the students' satisfaction on online lessons. The data were analyzed by mean, standard deviation value.

IV. RESULTS

A. Website for Online Learning System

The content structure of online learning system is

constructed from Bachelor of Art Curriculum for Business English Program containing 10 lessons (Unit 1 Let me give you my card?, Unit 2 I start work at 8.30, Unit 3 What does your company do?, Unit 4 How do you like your job?, Unit 5 Can I take a message?, Unit 6 Which ones should we order?, Unit 7 Are you free on Tuesday?, Unit 8 Where's the marketing department?, Unit 9 How long does the process take?, and Unit 10 Exports increased sharply). It also has exercises and tests in each unit for students to practice those skills on listening, speaking, reading and writing.

The website construction includes the processes as follow:

(a) study the course description for English for Business Communication (b) define the objectives and (c) construct the lessons-containing vocabulary, expressions, structures, exercises, tests and questionnaires and also adding other activities such as web board, movie, songs.

The website is provided at www.ssr.u.ac.th/teacher/suwaree. It shows the homepage, discussion web board, assessment report of overall course grading, and bar graph of number of students achieving grade ranges as the Figs. 1-4 below:

Fig. 1 Online system homepage

Fig. 2 Discussion web board

Name	Pre-test 1	Unit 1	Unit 2	Unit 3	Unit 4	Take home exam	Course total
Panupong	8.00	10.00	10.00	10.00	10.00	10.00	96.67
Nongnapat	6.25	10.00	10.00	10.00	10.00	10.00	93.75
Tasneeporn	4.75	10.00	10.00	10.00	10.00	10.00	91.25
Kaisorn	9.63	10.00	10.00	10.00	10.00	10.00	99.38
Jirawan	5.25	10.00	10.00	10.00	10.00	10.00	92.08

Fig. 3 Assessment report of the overall course grading

Fig. 4 Number of students achieving grade ranges

B. Satisfaction on Convenient Aspects

The average of satisfaction on convenient aspects is high level at 3.84. The most averages are information of the online system is interesting and update (3.97), response to the students' purposes (3.91), convenient and suitable for use (3.91), respectively. The least average is correcting and systematic system. The students satisfy on interesting and update because there are many activities for language practicing such as movies, songs, etc. and also other links for their self-interest practice. This is shown in Table I.

C. Satisfaction on Academic Aspects

Online lessons for English for Business Communication majors are used at www.ssr.u.ac.th/teacher/suwaree. It is based on Moodle Program containing course content, exercises, tests, web board, and other supplementary lessons such as movies, listening conversation, and structures. It is for the students to practice and search for information. The teacher will register for the students to access the website. The other main function is an information managing system; that is, the teacher can add or delete the information by him/herself including evaluation and report system such as menu bars, test results, and test analysis.

The results were found that the average of satisfaction on academic aspects is high level at 4.36. The most averages are technological searching tool through E-learning system that support the students' learning (4.51), knowledge evaluation on pre-post learning and teaching (4.45), and change for project selections according to their interest, subject contents including practice in the real situations (4.45), respectively.

The least average is on supporting the class climate to contribute students' language learning because sometimes there are no computer laboratory rooms available and some problems on adding students' name lists in the course cannot be solved by the language teacher. It still needs help from the information technology technician as shown in Table II.

TABLE I
SATISFACTION ON CONVENIENT ASPECTS

Item lists	\bar{x}	S.D.
The system is easy to use.	3.79	.739
The working system is rapid for use.	3.78	.704
It is a correct and systematic system.	3.76	.730
It response the students' purposes.	3.91	.742
The design is comprehensible and not complicated.	3.78	.855
The information is interesting and update.	3.97	.706
It is convenient and suitable for use.	3.91	.701
Total	3.84	.739

TABLE II
SATISFACTION ON ACADEMIC ASPECTS

Item lists	\bar{x}	S.D.
They response to purposes, objectives, learning activities of the course.	4.41	.567
They have the accordance with the documents of the subject as books and handouts.	4.31	.608
They help the class climate to contribute students' language learning.	4.21	.724
They support the students to participate and giving opinions in the pedagogy.	4.44	.633
They make it easier for language learning.	4.26	.631
They have other learning resources for further study for the student self-study.	4.34	.655
They are suitable tools for supporting students' learning.	4.35	.677
They support the students to have more aspects on learning interests.	4.25	.720
They have students knowledge evaluation on pre-post learning and teaching.	4.45	.549
They have a channel for informing the students about their feedback, correction, and suggestion on their mistakes.	4.35	.576
They have fair and suitable criteria on assessment and evaluation.	4.29	.732
They are flexible and response to students' need.	4.40	.542
They encourage the students to have creative thinking and evaluation.	4.39	.606
They give the change for project selections according to their interest, subject contents including practice in the real situations.	4.45	.571
They open the chance for sharing their ideas with their friends and teacher on discussion and group activities.	4.35	.638
They are a technological tool in the classroom for data search through E-learning system that support the students' learning.	4.51	.551
Total	4.36	.623

D. Satisfaction on Teaching Strategic Aspects

The overall mean score of satisfaction on teaching strategic aspects is 4.375 (SD 0.606). The all scores on teaching strategic aspects are at good satisfaction level (4.29-4.45). In general, the students are most satisfied with having student's knowledge evaluation on pre-post learning and teaching (4.45), responding to purposes, objectives, learning activities of the course (4.41), and having a channel for informing the students about their feedback, correction, and suggestion on their mistakes (4.35), respectively shown in Table III.

TABLE III
SATISFACTION ON TEACHING STRATEGIC ASPECTS

Item lists	\bar{x}	S.D.
They respond to purposes, objectives, learning activities of the course.	4.41	.567
They have student's knowledge evaluation on pre-post learning and teaching.	4.45	.549
They have fair and suitable criteria on assessment and evaluation.	4.29	.732
They have a channel for informing the students about their feedback, correction, and suggestion on their mistakes.	4.35	.576
Total	4.375	0.606

The concept of using online system in the classroom incorporates with Model 5. It identifies aim or objectives, organizing the contents, learning activities, following by an assessment/evaluation process.

E. Satisfaction on Facilitator Aspects

The overall mean score of satisfaction on facilitator aspects is 4.312 (SD 0.650). The all scores on facilitator aspects are at good satisfaction level (4.21-4.44). In general, the students are most satisfied with supporting the students to participate and giving opinions in the pedagogy (4.44), having other learning resources for further study for the student self-study. (4.34), and having the accordance with the documents of the subject as books and handouts (4.31), respectively. This is shown in Table IV.

TABLE IV
SATISFACTION ON FACILITATOR ASPECTS

Item lists	\bar{x}	S.D.
They have the accordance with the documents of the subject as books and handouts.	4.31	.608
They help the class climate to contribute students' language learning.	4.21	.724
They support the students to participate and giving opinions in the pedagogy.	4.44	.633
They make it easier for language learning.	4.26	.631
They have other learning resources for further study for the student self-study.	4.34	.655
Total	4.312	0.650

For using online system in the classroom, the teacher's role is a facilitator rather than the content authority. As Michael Sunnarborg's article, he reports that "Facilitation makes the learners responsible for their own learning. While this is a classic classroom strategy, it works in e-Learning too! Here's how you can bring your learners to that 'lightbulb moment' even if they are thousands of miles away." This study result is accordance to his concept that "The facilitator's role is to introduce subjects of discussion, encourage sharing of perspectives, and integrate students' shared experiences. This collaborative approach reinforces more of the 70% in the 70/20/10 formula — 70% of what we learn is on the job and through our experiences." [5], [6].

F. Satisfaction on Student-Centered Learning Aspects

The overall mean score of satisfaction on student-centered learning aspects is 4.385 (SD 0.615). The all scores on student-centered learning aspects are at good satisfaction level (4.25-4.51). In general, the students are most satisfied with a

technological tool in the classroom for data search through E-learning system that supports the student's learning (4.51), giving the change for project selections according to their interest, subject contents including practice in the real situations (4.45), and are flexible and response to students' need.(4.40), respectively shown in Table V.

TABLE V
SATISFACTION ON STUDENT-CENTERED ASPECTS

Item lists	\bar{x}	S.D.
They are flexible and response to students' need.	4.40	.542
They encourage the students to have creative thinking and evaluation.	4.39	.606
They give the change for project selections according to their interest, subject contents including practice in the real situations.	4.45	.571
They support the students to have more aspects on learning interests.	4.25	.720
They open the chance for sharing their ideas with their friends and teacher on discussion and group activities.	4.35	.638
They are a technological tool in the classroom for data search through E-learning system that supports the students' learning.	4.51	.551
They are suitable tools for supporting students' learning.	4.35	.677
Total	4.385	0.615

Student-centered process model is a main point of this study "learning by using online system". The process is thoroughly designed to be an ongoing process, created information and practice, including planned the learning environment for student's interest based. Especially, their activity selected from each of student's group in making decisions about topic and content. However, to solve the cohort effect, learning by using online system can add more content covering from cohort to cohort. The online can provide that by making more other complementary links to the lessons such as songs, movies, etc.

V. DISCUSSION

The Online Learning system is developed from using Moodle program including course materials and practice quizzes, interactive whiteboard or discussion web board to exercise and test applied English online. The structure of curriculum framework includes results of learning process, content, activity, media or innovation, measurement or evaluation, indicators, results of creating a course, English lesson plans based on the designed structure [7]. After students complete the listening and speaking exercises online, data management systems within Moodle, it is able to collect this data for the instructors to analyze and process the test results quickly.

Research results showed that students were satisfied with the overall level of the virtual classroom, online learning system that the teacher created. Students are able to learn at their own pace provided by the virtual classroom because of the discussion board, a large classroom of students can interact with the instructor easily. It is according to The National Education Act in 1999 focuses on the learning process, learner-centered educational, technology and

resources to expand services and provide opportunities for the students to play a role in the development of their full potential [7], [8].

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REFERENCES

- [1] Finocchiaro. (1989). English as a Second/Foreign Language: From Theory to Practice. Englewood Cliffs, N.J.: Prentice Hall Regents.
- [2] Great Schools Partnershp. (2013). The Glossary of Education Reform. Retrieved from: <http://edglossary.org/student-centered-learning/> April 10, 2014.
- [3] K. Youngs. (2014). Introduction to e-learning. Retrieved from: <http://www.jiscdigitalmedia.ac.uk/guide/introduction-to-elearning> May 5, 2014.
- [4] S.Yordchim. (2014). The Development on Business English Competency of Undergraduates with Online Learning System. Bangkok: Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University.
- [5] L. Brady. (1995). *Curriculum development*, 5th edn. Sydney: Prentice-Hall.
- [6] M. Sunnarborg. (2008). Learning Solutions Magazine. "From teacher to facilitator". Retrieved from <http://www.learningsolutionsmag.com/articles/74/from-teacher-to-facilitator> March 12, 2014.
- [7] S. Yordchim. (2010). Area Based Development Research Journal. "The Development of English Learning Process and English Teacher for Tourism in Local Area: Attractions in Bangkok Areas". Vol. 2 No.6 Jul.-Aug. Bangkok: Offset Plus.
- [8] Office of the National Education Commission. (1999). The National Education Act. Bangkok: Prig wan Communication.